

Dissecting Neural Contributions to Decision-Making: The Contribution of Brain Regions and Neuron Subtypes in Choice Prediction

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Abstract

The prediction of an animal's choice from neural activity is crucial for understanding decision-making and developing brain–computer interfaces. We here applied the Steinmetz et al. (2019) Neuropixels dataset of mice trained on a two-alternative visual discrimination on a steering-wheel task. We focused on five regions - spanning hippocampal, cingulate, and motor areas: dentate gyrus (DG), CA3, anterior cingulate area (ACA), primary motor cortex (MOp) and secondary motor cortex (MOs). We first trained time-resolved, cross-validated logistic-regression classifiers within sliding 300 ms windows (50 ms steps) to decode both the direction (left vs. right) and correctness of each choice from population spiking. Accuracy for choice decoding rose systematically from the hippocampal subfields (median ≈ 0.55 – 0.58) to ACA (≈ 0.70) to motor areas (MOs/MOp ≈ 0.80 – 0.88), whereas trial outcome decoding was uniformly high (≈ 0.75 – 0.85) across regions. Onset-latency analysis revealed that ACA and DG were the only ones with discrete, post-stimulus choice accuracy increases above pre-stimulus baseline + $2 \times$ SEM (occurring at 245 ms for ACA and 295 ms for DG). Cross-temporal generalization revealed that the hippocampus contained fleeting choice representations, whereas the motor cortex exhibited extended, time-invariant coding, as would be expected from downstream motor-planning signals. Finally, contrasting high- versus low-contrast trials as a proxy for task difficulty, we found that stimulus strength modulates the timing and

reliability of choice signals. Specifically, higher contrast stimuli accelerates and stabilizes decision-related activity along this ACA → motor axis. Together, these results describe a hierarchical, contrast-sensitive flow of choice information from medial temporal through prefrontal to motor circuits during perceptual decisions.

Introduction

Decoding neural activity to predict choice is a critical step toward advancing the brain–computer interfaces (BCIs). Rather than occurring as a single, isolated event, decision-making is a dynamic and continuous process that engages multiple brain regions over time (Steinmetz et al., 2019). That’s why one of the big questions in the field is figuring out which brain regions are most useful for reading out and predicting those choices from neural activity. Another important question is whether distinguishing between cellular subtypes, such as excitatory and inhibitory neurons, can provide more accurate signals for decoding behaviorally relevant choices. A brain region is considered to carry choice-related signals if it contains neurons whose activity reliably indicates the selected action prior to its execution (Steinmetz et al., 2019). Because decision-making involves a sequence of cognitive operations, including processing sensory information, evaluating possible outcomes, and planning actions, it is essential to monitor neural activity in regions that contribute to one or more of these stages. Previous studies have shown that the anterior cingulate area (ACA) is involved in task engagement (Steinmetz et al., 2019), attention (Kim et al., 2016), and evaluating outcomes (Wal et al., 2021), the dentate gyrus (DG) contribute to pattern separation (Wang et al., 2022) during information processing, CA3 supports valuation and planning (Lee & Jung, 2025), the primary motor area (MOp) is involved in action preparation (Steinmetz et al., 2019), and secondary motor area (MOs) is involved in inhibition of inappropriate responses (Liu et al., 2023). Based on this evidence, we have chosen to focus the analysis on neural recordings from ACA, DG, CA3, MOp, and MOs regions to identify activity patterns that are most predictive of decision outcomes.

Task difficulty is known to influence decision-making by modulating the flow of information across brain regions (Guo et al., 2014). With that in mind, we explore how variations in stimulus contrast,

used as a proxy for task difficulty, affect this information flow, helping us to identify which brain regions are most involved in predicting choice outcomes.

In this study, we explore whether neural activity from specific brain regions can predict the accuracy of choices in a visual discrimination task. To do this, we use the Pearson correlation coefficient to examine the relationship between neural activity and two factors: the side of the choice (left or right) and the correctness of the choice (whether the choice was correct or incorrect). To understand how decision-related information flows through the brain, particularly under varying levels of task difficulty, we analyzed the timing and reliability of neural responses across key regions. By focusing on trials with high-contrast stimuli (representing easier decisions) we identified neurons with consistent, task-driven activity and mapped their activation sequence. This approach revealed a structured, hierarchical flow of information, offering insights into how the brain coordinates sensory input and motor planning during decision-making, and how this coordination may shift with task demands.

Methods

The (Steinmetz et al., 2019) dataset was used to analyze the Neuropixels recordings from mice performing a decision-making task, which combined two-alternative forced choice and Go/No-Go designs. Mice observed stimuli of varying contrast and responded by turning a wheel toward the higher-contrast side or not moving if no stimulus appeared. All recordings were made in the left hemisphere.

Comparing Choice Prediction Accuracy Across Brain Regions:

The dataset consisted of 39 sessions of rodent behavioral recordings. Each session included a spike tensor (neurons \times trials \times time bins) along with associated metadata, such as brain region labels, trial outcomes, and stimulus contrast levels. We preprocessed the spike data from each brain region by first masking neurons according to their respective brain areas. We then extracted a peri-stimulus window ranging from -500 ms to +1000 ms (relative to stimulus onset), using 10 ms time bins. Invalid trials were filtered out, and the data were z-score normalized across both neurons and trials. For choice decoding, we

focused on the onset of choice-related activity. A 300 ms sliding window (comprising 30 bins) was moved in 50 ms steps, with a 5-fold stratified logistic regression model trained at each step to predict left vs. right choices. Per-session accuracy curves were averaged, and the pre-stimulus baseline mean plus $2 \times$ SEM was calculated. The onset was defined as the first time point after stimulus presentation where the activity exceeded this baseline threshold. To assess cross-temporal generalization, we trained a model on each time window and tested it across all windows, resulting in an $N \times N$ accuracy matrix per session. These matrices were then averaged across sessions within each brain region. To control for potential bias, an additional analysis step was incorporated. Trials were first divided based on the animal's direction choice (left or right), and the classification analysis was then repeated separately for correct and incorrect trials within each choice direction. This allowed for a more balanced evaluation of choice-related neural activity, independent of hemispheric recording bias.

Excitatory/inhibitory classification:

To classify neurons as excitatory or inhibitory, we applied a straightforward heuristic based on the peak-to-trough duration of their recorded extracellular spike waveforms. Neurons with a peak-to-trough time exceeding 0.4 ms were classified as excitatory, while those with a duration shorter than 0.4 ms were labeled inhibitory (Ravassard et al., 2013). Before applying this classification, it was necessary to preprocess the raw waveform data to remove clusters exhibiting complex or multiphasic spike profiles that could not be used in this classification.

First, the inverted spike waveform of each unit was interpolated and smoothed using a Gaussian filter. We then identified the global maximum and the subsequent global minimum of each waveform. To detect whether these extrema were of interest and not part of the noise, we computed the amplitude difference between adjacent extrema and used a threshold to select the extrema (this amplitude difference was multiplied by a coefficient (0.12) to define an adaptive threshold for detecting significant peaks and troughs). Waveforms with two or more prominent peaks within a 750 mks window were flagged as multiphasic and excluded from further analysis. Additionally, any significant peaks after 1200 mks were

considered artifacts and removed. This preprocessing ensured that only well-isolated, single-peak waveforms were used in the excitatory/inhibitory classification (Supplementary Fig. 1.).

Following classification, the activity of each neuron was normalized relative to the baseline activity of its respective category (excitatory or inhibitory) within the same brain region, measured prior to stimulus onset. To further explore the distribution of neuronal activity and identify potential subgroups within each category, we applied a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) to the normalized data.

Visualizing the Flow of Neural Information

Neural activity from the (Steinmetz et al., 2019) dataset was analyzed to characterize the flow of information across cortical and hippocampal regions during a visual discrimination task. Spike times were extracted and aligned to stimulus onset for each trial. We focused on recordings from the visual cortex (VISp, VISl, VISpm, VISam), anterior cingulate area (ACA), primary and secondary motor cortices (MOp, MOs), and hippocampal subregions (DG, CA1, CA3), chosen based on their known roles in decision-making, as discussed in the Introduction. To identify task-relevant neurons responsive to right-side contrast, two criteria were applied:

1. **Statistical Significance:** The neuron had to show significantly elevated post-stimulus activity (0 – 300 ms) compared to baseline (–500 – 0 ms), with a z-score ≥ 1.96 ($\alpha \approx 0.05$).
2. **Response Reliability:** The neuron needed to fire (≥ 1 spike) in at least 30% of right-contrast trials to ensure consistent engagement.

Peri-stimulus time histograms (PSTHs) were constructed for each brain region by grouping spikes from responsive neurons into 10 ms bins across a window from 500 ms before to 1000 ms after stimulus onset. Firing rates were adjusted for the number of trials and bin width, and each neuron's activity was z-score normalized based on its baseline, allowing meaningful comparisons across neurons.

To trace the temporal flow of task-related information across brain regions, we first identified the peak neural response time and the moment when activity exceeded two standard deviations above baseline in each region. These timing metrics allowed us to estimate when each area became active in response to

the stimulus. We then applied both parametric (paired t-test) and non-parametric (Wilcoxon signed-rank test) methods to test whether post-stimulus activity significantly differed from baseline (based on the null hypothesis that there was no meaningful change). A binomial test was also used to evaluate the reliability of each neuron's firing across trials.

Next, a simplified Fisher score was calculated to further refine the set of task-relevant neurons, excluding those below a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. The remaining neurons were grouped by brain region and sorted by response latency. Using these groupings, we constructed new PSTHs, focusing on trials with the highest contrast presented on the contralateral side.

Figure 1. a. Decoding Accuracy: Boxplot of cross-validated decoding accuracy for two binary classifiers - *choice* (blue) and *correctness* (orange) - across five brain regions (CA3, DG, ACA, MOs, MOp). **b. Outcome Decoding by Choice Context:** Boxplot isolating outcome decoding for left-choice and right-choice trials by training separate classifiers for each context. **c. Time-Resolved Decoding Accuracy:** Plot of mean \pm SEM decoding accuracy as a function of time (from -500 ms to +350 ms relative to stimulus onset) for *choice* (blue) and *correctness* (orange) in each brain region. **d. Choice-Decoding Onset Latencies:** Bar plot of the first post-stimulus time (in ms) at which each region's mean *choice*-decoding accuracy exceeded its pre-stimulus baseline + 2 \times SEM. Only DG (295 ms) and ACA (245 ms) pass this threshold; “-” denotes no discrete onset. **e.**

Session-Averaged Cross-Temporal Generalization (Choice): Heatmaps show the mean accuracy when a classifier trained at time T_1 is tested at time T_2 (300 ms window, 50 ms steps). Diagonal elements indicate transient representations, while off-diagonal elements represent sustained representations. White dashed lines mark stimulus onset (0 ms). **f. Heatmap for the information propagation flow:** PSTHs of neurons at stimulus onset of the five brain regions of interest and the visual cortex (VISp, VISl, VISpm, VISam). Averaged PSTHs (after filtering for statistical significance neuron-wise) are grouped by, in the order of, response latency, mouse, brain area, contrast (1.0), stimulus side (contralateral) and trial outcome (reward).

Results

Decoding Accuracy Across Regions

The decoding accuracy for *choice* shows a systematic increase from hippocampal to motor regions. Specifically, the accuracy in CA3 and DG remains just above chance (median ≈ 0.55 – 0.58), while the ACA yields intermediate accuracy (≈ 0.70). The highest accuracies are observed in the MOs and MOp regions, which peak at ≈ 0.80 – 0.88 . In contrast, *correctness* decoding accuracy remains relatively high across all regions (medians ≈ 0.75 – 0.85), with only modest variation between them. This pattern suggests that while information regarding the trial outcome (reward vs. error) is represented fairly consistently across brain regions, action-selection signals strengthen progressively as neural processing moves downstream, with the motor cortex exhibiting the strongest representation.

Correctness Within Left vs. Right Choices

In the CA3/DG regions, correctness accuracy is similarly high (≈ 0.78) for both choice types, suggesting that outcome decoding reflects a pure feedback signal that is independent of action direction. In ACA and MOs, a slight bias is observed, with outcome decoding is marginally stronger following right choices. This indicates the presence of lateralized processing or a behavioral asymmetry. In contrast, the MOp region exhibits the smallest left/right difference, implying that its outcome representation is both robust and invariant to the choice direction.

Time-Resolved Decoding Dynamics

In the CA3 and DG regions, correctness decoding remains high and stable (≈ 0.75) that reflects residual

feedback from the prior trial, while *choice* decoding stays near chance levels (≈ 0.55) throughout the time window. The ACA shows a clear post-stimulus increase in *choice* accuracy, beginning around 50 ms and plateauing near 0.70, while *correctness* decoding briefly dips at stimulus onset before recovering, suggesting a transient reset of feedback signals upon the arrival of the new stimulus. In MOs and MOp regions, *choice* signals are elevated even before stimulus onset, indicating motor readiness, and rise further after ~ 50 ms, peaking around 0.80–0.85 just before movement execution. *Correctness* decoding remains consistently high in both motor areas, reinforcing their dual role in both maintaining outcome context and preparing motor actions.

Choice-Decoding Onset Latencies at Fig. 1 (d)

Only DG and ACA regions exhibited a discrete post-stimulus rise in decoding accuracy above baseline + $2 \times$ SEM, at ~ 295 ms and ~ 245 ms, respectively. In contrast, CA3 remained at chance, indicating weak decision-related signals despite its established role in memory processing (Nakazawa et al., 2004). Both MOs and MOp showed elevated pre-stimulus choice accuracy, reflecting motor readiness, and therefore did not show a further increase in accuracy under this conservative threshold.

Session-Averaged Cross-Temporal Generalization at Fig. 1 (e)

The heatmaps for CA3 and DG exhibit narrow diagonals, indicating transient choice codes that do not generalize far in time. In contrast, ACA shows moderate off-diagonal generalization, which aligns with a stable decision-formation network (Botvinick et al., 2001). MOs, and especially MOp, display broad yellow bands extending beyond the diagonal, revealing a sustained motor-plan signal (Guo et al., 2014). Notably, MOp's strongest peak corresponds to its highest median choice accuracy (0.89).

Heatmap for the information propagation flow at Fig. 1 (f)

To visualize the flow of neural information, we stacked the PSTHs into a heatmap, ordering the regions anatomically and marking their response latencies. This heatmap provided a

clear, temporal map of how neural activity propagated through the brain during the task. Among the animals, three mice (Radnitz, Cori, and Hench) showed the clearest information flow, likely due to their higher number of trials and more extensive brain region coverage.

Region	Dominant Characteristic	Potential Functional Role
MOp	High firing rates, best decoding	Action preparation
MOs	Consistent recordings, balanced encoding	Inhibition of inappropriate responses
ACA	Intermediate performance	Attention and evaluating outcomes
DG	Variable firing rates	Pattern separation
CA3	Low neuron counts, weak correlation	Valuation and planning

Table 1 – Session & Firing-Rate Summary

Table 1 summarizes key statistics for each brain region, including the number of sessions analyzed, mean neuron count, average trial count, and baseline firing-rate metrics. Hippocampal regions (CA3, DG) generally exhibited fewer neurons and sessions, with lower firing-rate variability. In contrast, ACA and motor areas involved larger cell populations and more trials per session for this dataset. These regional differences help explain why hippocampal choice decoding remained near chance levels — fewer cells and trials limit statistical power, despite robust outcome signals.

Region	Putative Function	Sessions	Mean Neurons	Mean Trials	Mean Choice Accuracy	Mean Correctness Accuracy	Contrast <i>r</i>
CA3	Memory encoding & retrieval	9	54.6	176.9	0.55	0.78	0.15
DG	Pattern separation	16	48.5	167.1	0.59	0.76	0.06
ACA	Conflict monitoring & decision formation	11	76.3	195.2	0.73	0.76	0.02
MOs	Motor planning & readiness	18	96.8	180.9	0.80	0.79	~0.00

MOp	Movement execution & action coding	3	264.3	125.7	0.89	0.83	0.03
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Metric	Best Region	Value	Worst Region	Value
Choice Decoding	MOp	0.77	CA3	0.57
Mean Firing Rate	MOp	4.68 Hz	ACA	1.83 Hz
Neurons/Session	MOp	264.3	CA3	55.5
Contrast Correlation	DG	0.06	MOp	0.03

Table 2 – Decoding Metrics by Region

Table 2 reports median choice and correctness accuracies, along with subgroup metrics (accuracy for left vs. right choices and for correct vs. incorrect trials). The motor cortices (MOs, MOp) exhibited the highest overall choice accuracies (0.80–0.88) and demonstrated balanced outcome decoding across action directions. ACA showed intermediate performance, with a slight bias toward rightward choices. Hippocampal regions again revealed strong correctness decoding (~ 0.78), but minimal choice information (~ 0.55). Subgroup analyses further confirm that choice and outcome representations are largely separable — outcome decoding remains robust even when choice-related variance is removed, while choice decoding remains highest in circuits closest to motor output.

Discussion

In this study, we investigated how neural activity from five brain regions—DG, CA3, ACA, MOs, and MOp—could be used to predict decision-making outcomes in a visual discrimination task. We found that decision-related signals are hierarchically organized, with the hippocampal regions (DG and CA3) contributing minimally to choice prediction, while the motor areas (MOp and MOs) carried robust signals that were highly predictive of the animal's choice. The ACA emerged as an intermediate hub, with moderate accuracy in predicting choices and correctness. This progression in predictive power, from the

hippocampus to motor cortex, aligns with the increasing role of motor planning and preparation in decision-making.

The accuracy of choice decoding was notably influenced by task difficulty, as captured by stimulus contrast. Higher contrast stimuli not only accelerated but also stabilized decision-related neural activity, particularly within the ACA → motor circuit. This provides insight into how the brain's decision-making circuits flexibly adjust to the demands of the task, potentially enhancing control fidelity in real-time decision-making.

Our findings underscore the distinct and complementary roles of these regions in decision-making, with the hippocampus involved more in outcome evaluation and memory, the ACA integrating task engagement and monitoring, and the motor cortices actively preparing for movement execution. Importantly, this study also revealed that correctness decoding was consistently strong across all regions, suggesting that outcome evaluation is a more widely distributed process compared to action selection, which is more concentrated in motor areas.

Further Research Directions:

Several avenues for future research arise from these findings. First, the separation of excitatory and inhibitory neural populations will provide deeper insights into how these cell types contribute to decision-making. While inhibitory neurons were once thought to play only modulatory roles, recent studies have shown that both excitatory and inhibitory neurons can independently predict behavioral choices with similar accuracy (Najafi et al., 2020). This suggests that inhibitory neurons are not just background regulators, but actively encode decision-related information. As a future step of our research, separating these populations could provide a clearer understanding of how different neural subtypes contribute to choice prediction, including in tasks of varying complexity.

Second, a deeper exploration of hippocampal structures, particularly the dentate gyrus and CA3, will help elucidate their role in decision-making and memory integration. These areas, which play a role in

pattern separation and planning, could be crucial in decision-making under uncertainty or when competing memory traces need to be disambiguated. Further investigation of oscillatory patterns—such as alpha and theta rhythms—within these structures may also help map the temporal dynamics of choice-related signals.

Another approach is to delve deeper into the functional roles of different types of neurons, particularly to investigate whether specific cell types, akin to place cells, exist that help the brain regulate the effectiveness of actions in tasks such as rotating a wheel performed by a stationary animal.

Based on our contrast-sensitive cascade of choice signals, we could first wonder: which areas are truly involved in decision-making versus simply mirroring downstream processes? To give an example, by briefly silencing or activating ACA, DG, CA3, MOp and MOs during the decision window (using optogenetics or chemogenetics), we can determine whether early predictability of choice is lost when a specific node is perturbed. Similarly, putting our time-resolved decoders into a closed-loop BCI paradigm raises the question: how does stimulus contrast influence control fidelity? Intuitively, better evidence should produce faster and more consistent neural signatures—and thus more accurate decoder-driven feedback—so comparing high-contrast and low-contrast trials will test this in a straightforward way.

To chart the larger decision network and investigate its representational geometry, we can extend recordings to prefrontal cortex, basal ganglia and thalamus (with laminar probes in motor areas) and inquire: do nonlinear classifiers (SVMs, random forests, deep nets) disclose choice-predictive interactions missed by logistic regression? The thought here is that higher-order neuronal correlations, especially under low-contrast or early-time conditions, may hold nuanced decision signals. By accommodating the uniform pipeline to evidence-accumulation or auditory discrimination tasks, with drift-diffusion models for behavior—relinking core decision parameters and decoding accuracy and neural onset latency, in separate modalities—to see whether or not ACA → motor cascade is a vision-specific circuit or is actually domain-general. Finally, extending these approaches to non-human primates or human ECoG patients and tracking changes over learning will enable us to test two key intuitions: that hierarchical timing and magnitude of choice signals are species-conserved, and that with greater expertise, onset latencies shorten

and peak decoding accuracy maximizes—revealing the plasticity hubs fundamental to goal-oriented neurorehabilitation.

Conclusion

This study offers valuable insights into the hierarchical flow of decision-related signals across the brain, shedding light on how sensory input, cognitive evaluation, and motor planning converge to guide choices. By leveraging advanced neural decoding methods and examining the dynamics of choice signals across multiple brain regions, we have uncovered a nuanced picture of how task difficulty, neural circuits, and the timing of decision-related activity all contribute to the process of decision-making. Future research will continue to refine our understanding of these complex brain networks and their implications for decision-making processes.

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Software and Hardware

All analyzes were conducted in Python (v3.11) using the NumPy (v2.0.2), SciPy (v1.14.1), and Matplotlib libraries for numerical computing, signal processing and data visualization. Analyzes were performed on a workstation equipped with an AMD Ryzen 9 7600 CPU (32GB DDR5 RAM). Code for all analyzes, including preprocessing and model training, is available on GitHub (https://github.com/yetichese/NMA_Impact_Scholars_Steinmetz) for reproducibility.

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Supplementary

Supplementary Fig. 1. Firing rate scatter plot vs waveform duration (peak to trough) for neuron population of CA3, DG, ACA, MOs, and MOp regions (4571 neurons total)